

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

2,2'-Dipyridyl Complexes of Re(IV) and Re(V)

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The preparation and the properties of a few 2, 2'-dipyridyl complexes of Re(IV) and Re(V), e.g., $[\text{Re}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_4]$ and two forms of $[\text{ReO}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_3]$, were reported in an earlier communication¹. The isolation and the properties of some other 2, 2'-dipyridyl complexes are presented here.

$(\text{dipy H})_2 [\text{ReBr}_6]$ was prepared by metathesis between $\text{K}_2 [\text{ReCl}_6]$ and 2,2'-dipyridyl in 0.4 N hydrobromic acid medium. On heating this yellow substance in a current of nitrogen at 190° it lost 32.5% in weight and gave scarlet red $[\text{Re}(\text{dipy})\text{Br}_4]$. Oxidation with alkali chromate confirmed the oxidation state of rhenium in this complex as +4. This is insoluble in water, and in ethanol but moderately soluble in acetone. It was paramagnetic, the corrected magnetic moment being 3.40 B.M. at 300°K.

$[\text{ReO}(\text{dipy})\text{Br}_3]$ in green micro crystalline form was deposited by boiling under reflux perchloric acid with excess of 2,2'-dipyridyl and hypophosphorous acid in ethanol and hydrobromic acid. Green form of analogous chloro complex¹, $[\text{ReO}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_3]$, was also obtained in a similar method replacing hydrobromic acid with hydrochloric acid. Both were diamagnetic, but after diamagnetic corrections were made weak paramagnetism ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=0.43$ and 0.33 B.M. for the chloro and bromo complexes respectively) remained for Re(V). Both these were practically nonconducting in nitrobenzene. The infrared spectrum of the green form of $[\text{ReO}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_3]$ was very similar to that of the pale khaki coloured $[\text{MoO}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_3]$ recently reported by Mitchell² and gave, like the latter, important bands at 1610s, 1590w, 1450s, 1320s, 1310w, 1290w, 1248m, 1226w, 1170m, 1130w, 1115m, 1082w, 1070w, 1050w, 1025w, 988vs, 972w, 952w, 801w, 772vs, 745w, 724s cm^{-1} .

The violet form¹ of $[\text{ReO}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_3]$ was paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.08$ at 303° K).

On refluxing a suspension of the green form of $[\text{ReO}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_3]$ in rectified spirit with excess of 2,2'-dipyridyl, a violet solution was obtained from which sodium perchlorate gave a precipitate of violet $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{dipy})_2] (\text{ClO}_4)_2$. This was also obtained by precipitating the violet mother liquor of the violet form¹ of $[\text{ReO}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_3]$ with sodium perchlorate. The reactions occurring in these two preparations are probably as follows:

1. M. C. Chakravorti, this *Journal*, 1965, 42, 503.

2. J. Mitchell, *Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 23, 963.

$[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})(\text{dipy})_2] (\text{ClO}_4)_2$ is sparingly soluble in water and in ethanol. Its corrected magnetic moment was 0.84 B.M. at 303°K.

Refluxing of the green form of $[\text{ReO}(\text{dipy})\text{Cl}_2]$ in rectified spirit with excess of 2,2'-dipyridyl and sodium acetate gave a blue solution from which sodium perchlorate gave a blue-violet precipitate of $[\text{ReO}_2(\text{dipy})_2] \text{ClO}_4$.

The blue solution of $[\text{ReO}_2(\text{dipy})_2] \text{ClO}_4$ on acidification turns violet. These cationic complexes are similar to the corresponding pyridine complexes³, $[\text{ReO}_2\text{py}_4]^+$ and $[\text{ReO}(\text{OH})\text{py}_4]^{+2}$.

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3. V. V. Lebedinskii and B. N. Ivanov-Emin, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1959, 4, 794.